

Electro-organic synthesis of 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-aminoimidazole in acidic medium

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Abstract : Electro-organic synthesis of 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-aminoimidazole has been carried out by the constant current electrolysis at copper and amalgamated forms of copper and lead electrodes under acidic conditions. The electro reduction of 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (Ornidazole) has been also studied by cyclic voltammetry at glassy carbon electrode under acidic conditions which indicate the reducible behaviour of it. Isolated product was characterized by TLC, usual laboratory qualitative tests and IR, NMR spectral analysis. Effect of different parameters like current density, temperature, depolarizer concentration and nature of cathode material on yield percentage and current efficiency have been investigated. Number of electrons have also been calculated to confirm the isolated product, which is 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole.

Keywords : Constant current electrolysis, Ornidazole, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Nitroimidazole derivatives contain toxic selectivities to anaerobic micro-organism¹. The most important derivatives contain the 5-nitroimidazole nucleus with substituents at N1 position of the ring². Ornidazole, 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (molecular formula $C_7H_{10}N_3O_3Cl$; molecular weight 219.5) is almost crystalline powder soluble in methanol.

Ornidazole belongs to nitroimidazole group of drugs. This is anti-parasitic drug used against protozoan infections and widely known through Europe and the Third World as treatment for a variety of amoebic and parasitic infections. This drug has activity against *Peptococcus*, *Peptostreptococcus*, *Gardnella vaginalis*, *Clostridium*, *Propiobacterium*, *Eubacterium*, *Fuscobacterium*, *Bacteroides*, *Helicobacterium*, *Camphylobacterium*, *Actinomyces* and *Spirochetes*³. It is effective against *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Giardia intestinalis*⁴⁻⁶ and *Trichomonas vaginalis* and useful in Crohn's disease and *Pseudomembraneous colitis*⁷.

It also helps easy extraction of Guinea worm and also sensitizes hypoxic tumor cells to the effects of ionizing radiations⁸. Ornidazole may also be used to treat or prevent a variety of bacterial infections⁹, including *Helicobacter pylori*.

Considering the range of activity and non-emergence of resistance to most organisms¹⁰, nitroimidazole have become indispensable drugs in clinical practice. Hence adverse drug reactions (ADR) due to this group of drugs is very relevant. The antimicrobial activity of Ornidazole is due to the reduction of nitro group to a more reactive amine that attacks microbial DNA and brings about loss of helical structure of DNA and subsequent DNA breakage thus inhibiting further synthesis and causing degradation of existing DNA¹¹⁻¹⁴. This drug is readily absorbed from gastro-intestinal tract.

The voltammetric techniques showed themselves to be an excellent alternative for the study of the reaction mechanism¹⁵⁻¹⁷ and analytical determination of drugs, especially heterocyclic nitro compounds¹⁸. Compared with other methods developed for Ornidazole determination, this new procedure, cyclic voltammetry possesses advantages, such as, low detection limit, rapid response, excellent reproducibility, simplicity and low-cost¹⁹. Cyclic voltammetric studies of Ornidazole have been carried out at glassy carbon electrode under acidic condition. Typical cyclic voltammograms for Ornidazole are recorded within the wide range (200 mV to -1600 mV) of the

Where R = -CH₂-CH(OH)CH₂Cl, (A) = Ornidazole

Scheme 1

potential at pH 3.0 and at different scan rates (Fig. 1). The shapes of CVs clearly indicates that the reduction is irreversible and only one reduction wave is observed in cyclic voltammetry at pH 3.0 for Ornidazole. Anodic waves did not appear under any circumstances²⁰.

Fig. 1. Effect of scan rate on cyclic voltammetric behaviour of Ornidazole at pH 3.0. Parameters : IP, 200 mV; FP, -1600 mV; SR, 50, 100, 200, 500 mV s⁻¹; CS, µA; pH, 3.0; conc. 10 mM.

Electrochemical reduction of nitro compounds strongly depends on the pH of medium. General mechanism of reduction of nitro compounds in different media can be given as :

(i) In acidic medium (under high proton availability situation) :

The reduction of the nitroimidazole is a complex process, involving six electrons for complete reduction of the nitro group to the amine derivative²¹⁻²⁵ (Scheme 1).

Under anaerobic conditions or low oxygen pressure, the reduction process is similar to that of observed for nitrobenzene²⁶. The reduction mechanism for several aromatic and heterocyclic nitro compounds was presented by Zuman and coworkers²⁷⁻³⁵. A total of two electrons

and two protons are involved in the formation of the nitroso (R-NO) intermediate and two more electrons and protons result in the hydroxylamine (R-NHOH)³⁶.

The addition of two more electrons results in the formation of the amine.

(ii) In neutral and basic medium (under the condition of low proton availability) :

Scheme 2

Generally the $E_{1/2}$ values for the nitro group reduction change with the lateral chain at the N1 position of the heterocyclic ring³⁷⁻⁴⁰. Some compounds showed only one reduction wave involving six electrons in acidic medium.

The mercury electrode was mostly used, but good results were obtained at solid electrodes when studying nitrobenzene and nitroimidazole⁴¹.

The possibilities of the formation of the aminoimidazole and hydroxylamine imidazole were explored whenever the reaction performed under acidic, neutral and basic medium respectively. Six- and four-electrons changes

occur with the formation of corresponding product in acidic and basic medium respectively. Present work describes cathodic behaviour of Ornidazole in acidic medium using galvanostatic technique.

Experimental

Ornidazole was in tablet form i.e. Ornidazole 500 (Dazolic make) and other chemicals like sodium hydroxide, sulphuric acid, diethyl ether etc. were of analytical grade. All the solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Electrolytic cell used was a 250 ml beaker (tall form) with the provision of porous pot, magnetic stirrer, magnet bar, thermometer, cathode and agar-agar gel, glass tube (bridge) to measure the cathodic potential (vs saturated calomel electrode, SCE). Other components of the cell assembly were as follows⁴²⁻⁴⁴.

Cathode	: different metal strips
Catholyte	: 1% (v/v) aqueous sulphuric acid and methanol in 3 : 1 (v : v) ratio solution + Ornidazole tablets
Total volume of catholyte	: 100 ml
Anode	: lead strip (PbO ₂)
Anolyte	: aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid
Distance between cathode and anode	: 2.5 cm (approximately)

Catholyte prepared was of different concentration from 0.5 g/100 ml to 1.5 g/100 ml. The temperature was controlled to the desired value by adding ice cold water in outer jacket of electrolysis cell. A magnetic stirrer was used for agitation.

The desired current according to current density range was applied from the current regulated power supply (galvanostat) developed by CDPE (Centre for Development of Physics Education), University of Rajasthan, Jaipur. The cathodic potential measured by digital multimeter RISH Multi 14S via saturated calomel electrode (SCE) through agar-agar Gel Bridge in each case i.e. at all electrodes under investigation in the presence and absence of depolarizer to get suitable current density range for reduction under the experimental conditions imposed. In all cases a theoretical quantity of current was passed depending upon the amount of depolarizer taken.

After electrolysis, the catholyte was neutralized with 1% (w/v) sodium hydroxide solution and cooled to 278–283 K in ice. This solution was then treated with diethyl

ether to extract the product and the same was washed with ice-cold water to remove the acid or salt and allowed to evaporate the ether.

Analysis by physico-chemical methods :

Analysis of product had been carried out by usual physico-chemical methods. The product was highly viscous and dark brownish in color. Product, was also characterized by C, H analyzer and spectrophotometric techniques such as, IR and NMR.

The following observations were made.

- (i) A single clear spot on silica gel-G plate was obtained in iodine chamber (80% C₆H₆ + 20% ethyl acetate medium) confirming that the product was a single compound and not a mixture.
- (ii) Usual tests, for nitro-group in the product, gave a negative test, however, test for amine gave positive results.
- (iii) The percentage of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen in the product was determined by Perkin-Elmer elemental analyzer.
- (iv) IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Shimadzu 400-50 infrared spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹).
- (v) ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL AL 300 NMR spectrophotometer using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm). Structure of product represented with value of chemical shift of protons in δ ppm illustrated in Structure 1.

C, H, N estimation value :

The observed values of the carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen, in the product, were 21.66, 4.3, 19.03%, respectively, as compared to their theoretical values, which are 21.86, 4.5, 19.13%, respectively, thus, confirming the product.

IR spectra :

IR spectra of 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-aminoimidazole showed sharp two spikes peak of (-NH₂) at 3370 cm⁻¹ i.e. characteristic peaks, which shows nitro group completely reduced to amino group.

NMR spectra :

- (i) ¹H NMR of -NH₂ exhibited a broad singlet at δ 4.6 ppm.
- (ii) A singlet appeared at δ 7.4 ppm due to (N-CH-N) imidazole ring.
- (iii) Two doublet were observed at δ 4.21 ppm and 3.9

ppm, which attributed to $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$ proton, respectively.

- (iv) Two triplet for $-\text{CH}$ appeared at δ 4.1 ppm and 3.7 ppm due to $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$ proton, respectively.
- (v) A singlet for $-\text{OH}$ protons appeared at δ 2.8 ppm.
- (vi) A singlet appeared at δ 2.42 ppm due to $-\text{CH}_3$ protons from imidazole ring.

Structure 1. 1-(3-Chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-amino-imidazole.

Results and discussion

Polarization curves :

The polarization data are given in Tables 1(a), 1(b) and 1(c) from which polarization curves have been drawn for Ornidazole and are given in Figs. 2, 3 and 4 for all the electrodes investigated. Comparison of these polarization curves in presence and in the absence of depolarizer shows suitable current density ranges for reduction. The data for potential vs time curves are also given in Table 1(d) and curves have been drawn in Fig. 5.

Polarization curves for the reduction at lead and amal-

Fig. 2. Cathodic polarization curves of Ornidazole in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid + methanol medium, temp. $[298 \pm 1]$ at amalgamated copper (Cu-Hg) electrode : (○) blank (without depolarizer), (▲) with 0.5 M depolarizer, (×) with 0.1 M depolarizer, (■) with 0.2 M depolarizer.

gamated form of copper and lead (Cu-Hg and Pb-Hg) show that virtually polarization has been taken place and it is further confirmed by electrolysis for Ornidazole.

Table 1(a). Cathodic polarization data of Ornidazole at amalgamated copper (Cu-Hg) electrode in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid and methanol solution

Cathode area = 14.18 cm², Temp. = 25 ± 1 °C

Sl. no.	Current (Amp)	Current density (c.d., Amp cm ⁻²)	-log c.d.	Potential (-V) vs SCE			
				Without depolarizer	With depolarizer		
					0.5 g	1.0 g	1.5 g
1.	0.10	0.007	2.15	0.450	0.152	0.104	0.075
2.	0.20	0.014	1.85	0.450	0.152	0.104	0.075
3.	0.30	0.021	1.67	0.450	0.152	0.104	0.075
4.	0.40	0.028	1.55	0.450	0.152	0.104	0.075
5.	0.50	0.035	1.45	0.450	0.152	0.104	0.075
6.	0.60	0.042	1.37	0.970	0.190	0.139	0.105
7.	0.70	0.049	1.31	1.305	0.446	0.310	0.196
8.	0.80	0.056	1.25	1.426	1.525	1.326	1.132
9.	0.90	0.063	1.20	1.490	1.836	1.540	1.389
10.	1.00	0.070	1.15	1.557	-	-	-

Table I(b). Cathodic polarization data of Ornidazole at lead (Pb) electrode in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid and methanol solution

Cathode area = 12.80 cm², Temp. = 25 ± 1 °C

Sl. no.	Current (Amp)	Current density (c.d., Amp cm ⁻²)	-log c.d.	Potential (-V) vs SCE			
				Without depolarizer	With depolarizer		
					0.5 g	1.0 g	1.5 g
1.	0.10	0.0078	2.11	0.496	0.040	0.022	0.007
2.	0.20	0.0156	1.81	0.496	0.040	0.022	0.007
3.	0.30	0.023	1.64	0.496	0.040	0.022	0.007
4.	0.40	0.031	1.51	0.496	0.040	0.022	0.007
5.	0.50	0.039	1.41	0.496	0.040	0.022	0.007
6.	0.60	0.047	1.33	0.508	0.040	0.022	0.007
7.	0.70	0.055	1.26	0.950	0.788	0.096	0.058
8.	0.80	0.063	1.20	1.120	1.325	0.484	0.374
9.	0.90	0.070	1.15	1.280	1.540	1.132	0.986
10.	1.00	0.078	1.11	1.450	1.570	1.310	1.126

Table I(c). Cathodic polarization data of Ornidazole at amalgamated lead (Pb-Hg) electrode in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid and methanol solution

Cathode area = 12.80 cm², Temp. = 25 ± 1 °C

Sl. no.	Current (Amp)	Current density (c.d., Amp cm ⁻²)	-log c.d.	Potential (-V) vs SCE			
				Without depolarizer	With depolarizer		
					0.5 g	1.0 g	1.5 g
1.	0.10	0.0078	2.11	0.507	0.419	0.330	0.245
2.	0.20	0.0156	1.81	0.507	0.419	0.330	0.245
3.	0.30	0.023	1.64	0.507	0.419	0.330	0.245
4.	0.40	0.031	1.51	0.507	0.419	0.330	0.245
5.	0.50	0.039	1.41	0.507	0.419	0.330	0.245
6.	0.60	0.047	1.33	0.532	0.419	0.330	0.245
7.	0.70	0.055	1.26	1.080	0.433	0.386	0.291
8.	0.80	0.063	1.20	1.265	0.525	0.444	0.374
9.	0.90	0.070	1.15	1.390	1.150	0.973	0.768
10.	1.00	0.078	1.11	1.500	1.600	1.425	1.159
11.	1.10	0.085	1.06	1.610	1.750	1.565	1.264

Table I(d). Polarization data for long term electrolysis (potential vs time) of Ornidazole (1 g) at lead (Pb), amalgamated copper (Cu-Hg) and amalgamated lead (Pb-Hg) electrodes in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid and methanol solution

Temp. = 25 ± 1 °C

Sl. no.	Time (min)	Potential (-V) vs SCE at lead (Pb) electrode	Potential (-V) vs SCE at amalgamated copper (Cu-Hg) electrode	Potential (-V) vs SCE at amalgamated lead (Pb-Hg) electrode
1.	0	0.765	0.930	0.973
2.	20	0.894	0.986	1.005
3.	40	0.939	1.024	1.076
4.	60	1.046	1.104	1.150
5.	80	1.112	1.130	1.184
6.	100	1.154	1.200	1.240

Table-1(d) (contd.)

7.	120	1.154	1.200	1.240
8.	140	1.154	1.200	1.240
9.	160	1.154	1.200	1.240
10.	180	1.154	1.200	1.240

Fig. 3. Cathodic polarization curves of Ornidazole in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid + methanol medium, temp. $[298 \pm 1]$ at lead (Pb) electrode : (○) blank (without depolarizer), (▲) with 0.5 M depolarizer, (×) with 0.1 M depolarizer, (■) with 0.2 M depolarizer.

Fig. 4. Cathodic polarization curves of Ornidazole in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid + methanol medium, temp. $[298 \pm 1]$ at amalgamated lead (Pb-Hg) electrode : (○) blank (without depolarizer), (▲) with 0.5 M depolarizer, (×) with 0.1 M depolarizer, (■) with 0.2 M depolarizer.

The proper current density ranges to be 0.056 to 0.063, 0.063 to 0.078 and 0.070 to 0.085 Amp cm^{-2} for Cu-Hg, Pb and Pb-Hg electrodes respectively (Table 2).

After conducting experiments at various current densities optimum conditions have been determined for all three electrodes (Cu-Hg, Pb and Pb-Hg) are 0.056 for Cu-Hg and 0.070 Amp cm^{-2} for Pb and Pb-Hg Ornidazole (Table 3).

Conclusion :

The formation of 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-aminoimidazole by the electro reduction of 1-

Table 2. Effect of current density on yield at different cathodes [temperature 298 ± 1 K, catholyte 100 ml (aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid + methanol solution containing Ornidazole (1.0 g))]

Sl. no.	Cathode	Current density (Amp cm^{-2})	Yield of the product (%)
1.	Cu-Hg	0.056	69
		0.063	63
		0.063	62
2.	Pb	0.070	70
		0.078	65
		0.070	71
3.	Pb-Hg	0.078	63
		0.085	63

Table 3. Optimum conditions for electro reduction of Ornidazole (1 g) (medium : aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid \pm methanol solution)

Cathode	Temp. 298 \pm 1 K		
	Temperature (\pm 1 K)	Current density (Amp cm ⁻²)	Current efficiency (%)
Cu	298	0.056	86
Cu-Hg	298	0.070	89
Pb-Hg	298	0.070	93

(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole involves six electrons process (Scheme 1). This is confirmed by working electrode potential vs time curves (Fig. 5). It is seen from the curves that the cathodic potential becomes constant after theoretical time during electrolysis approximately required for six electrons process according to Faraday's law.

Fig. 5. Time vs potential curves of Ornidazole (1 g) in aqueous 1% (v/v) sulphuric acid + methanol medium : (▲) Cu-Hg (amalgamated copper) electrode, (○) Pb-Hg (amalgamated lead) electrode, (■) Pb (lead) electrode.

The compound prepared through this electrolytic method has a wide scope in pharmacological industry. The literature reviewed so far does not propose any method for the preparation of this compound on any scale. Thus, 1-(3-chloro-2-hydroxy propyl)-2-methyl-5-aminoimidazole can be prepared by the cathodic reduction of Ornidazole at any of the electrodes investigated.

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